

IR8, IR36, and IR46 for CGR (panicle initiation to heading); and IR36, IR42, and OM201 for HI.

Heterosis and heterobeltiosis for these traits in the selected crosses are presented in Table 2. Heterosis over midparents for

yield ranged from 23 to 63.6%; heterosis over better parents ranged from 6.8 to 62.5%. Most of the F_1 means of HDI deviated slightly from parental and mid-parental values in all crosses, indicating the absence of heterosis for the trait.

HI obtained high positive values in the divergent genotype cross of IR8/OM201. We also observed heterosis in the desirable direction in LAI, NAR, and CGR, from heading to ripening, in some crosses. ■

Breeding methods

Ability of some cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines of rice to produce hybrid seed

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We evaluated the ability of some CMS lines to establish satisfactory seed set with restorer (R) lines. A crossing block with 10 CMS and 5 restorer lines was laid out in a randomized block design with two replications during 1990 wet season. A line $\times$ tester model of crossing was used to make 50 crosses.

In both replications, each A line was flanked by a R line on both sides (1:2 ratio of A to R lines). Three staggered plantings of R lines at 5-d intervals were made to produce the continuous pollen supply that would ensure synchronized flowering of A and R lines. For each row, 15 plants for both A and R lines were maintained at 20- $\times$ 20-cm spacing.

We grew a row of Purple Puttu between crosses to intercept pollen.

We allowed the plants to outcross naturally. We aided pollination by tapping the R lines with bamboo sticks and passing ropes across the lines during anthesis. The hybrid seeds were collected at maturity from A lines. We used the mean seed set of 15 plants in each A line for the analysis.

The analysis of variance for seed set in a randomized block showed significant differences among the 50 crosses (see table). TNMS37 A/ARC11353 R recorded the maximum seed set (24.8%), followed by V20 A/IR54 R (24.4%). The line TNMS37 A crossed well with all R lines except IR36 R (2.25%); it had a mean seed set of 12.3%. When the mean seed set percentages of the R lines—in combination with all the A lines—were compared, IR46 R had the highest mean seed set of 12.3%, followed by IR54 R with 12%.

Because R lines combine differently with different male sterile lines, it is recommended that the parents be selected on the basis of seed set in

individual crosses rather than on their overall performance. In this context, the hybrids TNMS37 A/ARC11353 R, V20 A/IR54 R, and IR54756 A/IR54 R are the best combinations to produce increased hybrid seed. ■

Genetic analysis of yield components in rice involving CMS lines

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Success in breeding for quantitative traits depends upon the gene action involved for the traits concerned and the nature of the gene effects controlling the character.

We conducted a study to deduce the nature of gene action governing the traits that are economically important in rice. We used a line $\times$ tester method of mating. Ten cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines (IR54753, IR54756, V20, ZS97, Intan mutant, Pushpa, Mangala, Improved Sona, TNMS37, and ADCMS-1) were used as the lines. Five restorer lines (IR36, IR46, IR54, IR9761-19-1, and ARC11353) served as the testers.

Seed set in A/R crosses by natural outcrossing.

Male sterile line	Seed set (%)					Mean
	ARC11353 R	IR36 R	IR9761-19-1 R	IR46 R	IR54 R	
IR54753 A	13.40	5.60	2.19	17.70	7.84	9.35
Intan Mutant A	4.83	5.70	5.02	4.60	5.40	5.11
Z.S. 97 A	9.80	12.99	10.74	15.51	8.60	11.53
Pushpa A	13.40	5.29	4.30	6.90	12.90	8.56
Mangala A	6.40	2.26	0.39	12.14	6.00	5.44
IR54756 A	6.09	14.70	2.44	11.70	21.14	11.21
Improved Sona A	16.09	6.60	7.35	18.40	9.06	11.50
TNMS37 A	24.75	2.25	13.46	14.97	11.21	13.33
ADCMS-1-A	9.09	10.95	14.00	18.15	13.45	13.13
V20 A	12.25	15.45	3.90	2.40	24.36	11.67
Mean	11.61	8.18	6.38	12.25	12.00	-
SE (d) = 1.44						
LSD = 2.89						

Ratio of GCA and SCA variances.

Character	GCA variance (σ^2A)	SCA variance (σ^2D)	Ratio of $\sigma^2A:\sigma^2D$
Days to 50% flowering	7.03	11.43	0.62
Plant height	0.29	27.26	0.01
Productive tillers	0.09	1.56	0.06
Boot leaf area	1.77	16.26	0.11
Panicle exertion	0.48	1.30	0.37
Panicle length	0.05	1.76	0.03
Grains per panicle	92.90	186.34	0.50
100-grain weight	0.001	0.02	0.05
Grain yield	2.98	5.75	0.51